

DIDACTIC PRINCIPLES OF METHODOLOGY IN TEACHING MATHEMATICS IN PRIMARY GRADES

Hakimjonova Gavharxon Hasanboyevna

a teacher of primary school № 23 Dangara region, Uzbekistan.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7475718>

ABSTRACT: Mathematics is an important part of human life, so at school all children are taught for maths. The purpose of the article is to show some didactic principles of teaching mathematics in primary classes. Moreover, the article gives some strategies as well as ideas about teaching mathematics by great scholars of the world.

KEY WORDS: teaching mathematics, didactics, methodology, academic programs, mathematical development.

Social and economic relations in our country, changes in the public education system “Education in the Law on” and in the “National Personnel Training Program”, to each primary school teacher as indicated an important task is being set. These tasks are for elementary education allows you to distinguish a specific syllable, that these syllables are different of education in academic programs, curricula, textbooks to be introduced and to form a network in the methodical system.

State educational standards educational method to create complexes (program, curriculum, textbooks) opens wide opportunities, as well as interdisciplinary study based on the principle of connection and coordination of knowledge interrelationship of academic subjects and interdisciplinarity serves to provide.

The main didactic goals in mathematics lessons are:

Different didactic tools are used for each lesson. Among them, the main goal is one and it is the basis of the lesson is called a didactic purpose. The purpose of each individual lesson is the purpose of the system of lessons determining and using it the content of the subject being taught reveals to students. In this case with new concepts In order to introduce the student, in the second case, to expand the introduced concept, in the third case, something formation of competence and skills, in the fourth, knowledge, competence and skill testing etc. is done. Several of the above may be covered in each lesson. Is it passed? Reorganizing the previous lesson on repetition, thus it includes knowledge testing. Presentation of new material always followed by exercise.

Learning substantial math is critical for primary grade children. The early years are especially important for math development. Children’s knowledge of math in these years predicts their math achievement for later years—and

throughout their school career. Furthermore, what they know in math predicts their later reading achievement as well (Duncan et al. in press). Given that early math learning predicts later math and reading achievement, math appears to be a core component of learning and thinking.

All children have the potential to learn challenging and interesting math. Primary grade children have an often surprising ability to do abstract math—that is, math that is done by reasoning mentally, without the need for concrete objects. Listen to the worries of this first-grader. Primary grade children often know, and can definitely learn, far more challenging and interesting math than they are taught in most U.S. classrooms. That does not necessarily mean math pushed down from higher grades. It means letting children invent their own strategies for solving a variety of types of problems.

Understanding children’s mathematical development helps teachers be knowledgeable and effective in teaching math. Children’s thinking follows natural developmental paths in learning math. When teachers understand these paths and offer activities based on children’s progress along them, they build math learning environments that are developmentally appropriate and particularly effective. A useful tool in understanding and supporting the development of children’s mathematical reasoning is a math learning trajectory. There are learning trajectories for mathematics at all age levels, from birth throughout the school years, and for learning all kinds of content—from specific math concepts such as number and operations to specific science concepts like understanding electricity.

Math learning trajectories have three parts: a mathematical goal, a developmental path along which children’s math knowledge grows to reach that goal, and a set of instructional tasks, or activities, for each level of children’s understanding along that path to help them become proficient in that level before moving on to the next level. Let’s examine each of these three parts.

a) Goal. The first part of a learning trajectory is the goal. Goals should include the big ideas of math, such as “numbers can be used to tell us how many, describe order, and measure” and “geometry can be used to understand and to represent the objects, directions, and locations in our world, and the relationship between them” (Clements, Sarama, & DiBiase 2004). In this article, we look at the goal of knowing how to solve a variety of addition and subtraction problems.

b) Developmental path. The second part of a learning trajectory consists of levels of thinking, each more sophisticated than the last, leading to achieving the

mathematical goal. That is, the developmental path describes a typical learning route children follow in developing understanding of and skill in a particular mathematics topic. Learning trajectories are important because young children's ideas and their interpretations of situations are different from those of adults. Teachers must interpret what the child is doing and thinking and attempt to see the situation from the child's viewpoint. Knowledge of developmental paths enhances teachers' understanding of children's thinking, helping teachers assess children's level of understanding and offer instructional activities at that level. Similarly, effective teachers consider the instructional tasks from the child's perspective.

c) Instructional tasks. The third part of a learning trajectory consists of sets of instructional tasks or activities matched to each level of thinking in a developmental progression. The tasks are designed to help children learn the ideas and practice the skills needed to master that level. Teachers use instructional tasks to promote children's growth from one level to the next.

The three research findings—the importance of math learning in the primary grades, all children's potential to learn math, and teachers' need to understand children's learning development—have implications for teaching primary grade math well. We suggest the following approach:

- Know and use learning trajectories.
- Include a wide variety of instructional activities.

The learning trajectories provide a guide as to which activities are likely to challenge children to invent new strategies and build new knowledge.

- Use a combination of teaching strategies. One effective approach is to
 - (a) discuss a problem with a group,
 - (b) follow up by having children work in pairs, and then
 - (c) have the children share solution strategies back with the group.Discuss strategies with children in pairs and individually. Differentiate instruction by giving groups or individual children different problem types. Alexander and Entwisle state that “the early grades may be precisely the time that schools have their strongest effects” (1988, 114). Math is so important to children's success in school, in the primary grades and in future learning, that it is critical to give children motivating, substantive educational experiences. Learning trajectories are a powerful tool to engage all children in creating and understanding math.

The three research findings—the importance of math learning in the primary grades, all children's potential to learn math, and teachers' need to understand

children's learning development—have implications for teaching primary grade math well. We suggest the following approach:

- Know and use learning trajectories.
- Include a wide variety of instructional activities. The learning trajectories provide a guide as to which activities are likely to challenge children to invent new strategies and build new knowledge.
- Use a combination of teaching strategies. One effective approach is to (a) discuss a problem with a group, (b) follow up by having children work in pairs, and then (c) have the children share solution strategies back with the group. Discuss strategies with children in pairs and individually. Differentiate instruction by giving groups or individual children different problem types. Alexander and Entwisle state that “the early grades may be precisely the time that schools have their strongest effects” (1988, 114). Math is so important to children's success in school, in the primary grades and in future learning, that it is critical to give children motivating, substantive educational experiences. Learning trajectories are a powerful tool to engage all children in creating and understanding math.

References:

1. Rajapova, Malika. "BADIY MATNDA Q'LLANILUVCHI ALLEGORIK VOSITALARNING LINGVOKULTUROLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI." Scienceweb academic papers collection (2020).
2. Malika, Rajapova. "EFFECTIVE WAYS OF COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING ISSN: 2249-7137 Vol. 11." (2021).
3. Rajapova, M. (2021). LINGVOCULTUROLOGY AND ITS PECULIARITIES AS NEW BRANCHES OF CONTEMPORARY LINGUISTICS.
4. Rajapova, M. PRINCIPLES OF COGNITIVE METAPHOR AND ALLEGORY IN DISCOURSE. 2021.
5. Haydarova, Gulhayo. "Traditions And Peculiarities Of Alisher Navoi In The Uzbek Ghazal Of The Xx Century." The American Journal of Applied Sciences 2.13: 703.
6. Аҳмадалиевна, Ҳайдарова Гулҳаё. "НАВОИЙ ВА СОБИР АБДУЛЛА." ALISHER NAVOIY XALQARO JURNALI 1.2 (2021).
7. Ahmadaliyevna, Haydarova Gulhayo. "Talmeh or alluziya." ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal 11.9 (2021): 772-779.
8. Аҳмадалиевна, Ҳайдарова Гулҳаё. "СОБИР АБДУЛЛА, ЧАРХИЙ ВА ҲАБИБИЙ ҒАЗАЛИЁТИНИНГ ВАЗН ХУСУСИЯТЛАРИГА ДОИР." Conferencea (2022): 47-49.

9. Ahmadaliyevna, Haydarova Gulhayo. "Interpretation of the Image of the Heart in the Poems of Habibi, Charkhi and Sabir Abdullah." *European Multidisciplinary Journal of Modern Science* 6 (2022): 621-626.
10. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/hh-asr-zbek-azallarining-vazn-hususiyatiga-doir>
11. G. X. Boyquziyeva, and M. M. Jo'rayeva. "SOME FEATURES OF WOMEN'S SOCIAL ACTIVITIES IN UZBEKISTAN". *JournalNX - A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal*, vol. 8, no. 12, Dec. 2022, pp. 346-8, doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/AKB5Z.
12. G. H. Boykuziyev, and M. Azizova. "TRENDS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE SOCIAL POSITION OF WOMEN IN UZBEKISTAN AND SOCIO PHILOSOPHICAL VIEWS". *JournalNX - A Multidisciplinary Peer Reviewed Journal*, vol. 8, no. 12, Dec. 2022, pp. 392-5, doi:10.17605/OSF.IO/GRJF6.
13. Бойкузиева, Гузал. "ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ ЖЕНЩИН В СОЦИАЛЬНО-ПОЛИТИЧЕСКОЙ ЖИЗНИ ОБЩЕСТВА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ." *ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ПОДХОДЫ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКЕ*. 2020.

